

Advanced technical textiles and materials in defence: is the EU up to the challenge?

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to reflect on the challenges of adopting new technologies in Technical Textiles and Materials for defence concerning the current readiness and capacities in the European Union. Identified bottlenecks are the manufacturing readiness, the supply chain capacity and autonomy, and the knowledge and technical skills required.

INTRODUCTION

Defence forces on the various military domains heavily depend on Technical Textiles and Materials (TTM) to ensure their operational readiness. Standard features of TTM must provide several functional performance requirements: physical; environmental; camouflage, concealment and deception; protection against battlefield threats and hazards. Existing technologies already fulfil these requirements and are critical to delivering personal clothing and equipment to the Armed Forces. Some of these requirements are also relevant for other sectors, e.g. security forces, emergency personnel and firefighters, and other professions developed in hostile environments, enabling dual-use perspectives of employment for TTM.

The introduction of advanced materials in defence applications primarily attempts to fulfil current functional and operational requirements. Additionally, new applications and functionalities might result from applying the more elaborated features and complexity these materials provide. Some examples are wearable technologies, which will feed data to feed the common operational picture (COP), or dynamic functionalities to provide adaptive camouflage or energy harvesting and storing.

Independently of the technological sector, disruptive technologies always bring challenges that might stall or even deter its full adoption. This paper aims to revise standard requirements for defence applications, new applications of advanced materials and discuss eventual dysfunctionalities resulting from the adoption of disruptive technologies.

MILITARY REQUIREMENTS FOR DEFENCE TEXTILES AND MATERIALS

Standard requirements for textiles and materials used in combat systems and clothing are grouped according to the operational environment, functionality, or economic considerations [Scott, 2000]. These requirements mostly overlap, sometimes even conflict due to practical, ergonomic or physical constraints, to assure a safe and secure operation of personnel, weapons, and other battlefield systems.

The reduction of weight and volume, the increased comfort and durability/stability, the tactical performance (e.g. low noise emissions or antistatics behaviour), or the cleaning and maintenance are among the most relevant physical requirements. Even when facing normal environmental conditions, the capacity of textiles and materials for protection from water, flame, wind, temperature and light effects is vital for both the comfort of personnel and the safety of systems. The protection against environmental conditions is even more critical when facing extreme conditions that directly impact survivability and operability. Regarding camouflage, concealment and deception, the materials need to match the spectrum and blend into the surrounding environments typically observed/detected by the enemy forces in a wide range, including the radar, infrared, visual or ultraviolet spectrums. Protecting personnel and systems against CBRN hazards or battlefield threats, such as bullets, artefacts, or ballistic fragments, is critical for mission success.

On top of these technical requirements, there are economic considerations to be addressed. Given desired levels of operational capability and compliance with multiple international standards [STANREC 4833], public procurement imposes stringent acquisition processes. These rules will promote competitiveness among suppliers and sometimes compromise quality if rigorous control is not applied. Another economic consideration to be accounted for is the environmental impact of these materials along their complete lifecycle, from production to disposal.

TECHNOLOGY CONUNDRUMS

Advances in TTM, and manufacturing processes will certainly impact defence and national security over the coming decades. Emergent products and technologies, such as nano-, meta-, auxetic-, or multi-functional materials, or materials for energy storage and generation, have the potential to enable sound innovation. While allowing to fulfil standard requirements, these products and related technologies will undoubtedly promote innovation in defence applications [Marsili, 2021].

Disruptive developments resulting from governmental or industry-driven research and technology (R&T) efforts commonly face several paradoxical conundrums. A significant issue resides in concealing the technology readiness level (TRL) of given technologies and applications with the required industry's manufacturing readiness level (MRL) to ensure short-term sustainability. When the MRL for a given sector is low, the adoption of disruptive technologies with equally low TRL takes longer, is costly, and usually requires substantial public financing.

The defence industrial base is quite asymmetric for the European Union (EU) Member States (MS). Some MS procure defence products outside their borders, while other MS procure internally, strongly investing in R&T and promoting a highly specialised industrial base.

Another issue concerns the supply chains for raw and processed materials to be integrated into the TTM. The scale-up of production for these materials to be integrated into TTM is undoubtedly significant if tied to low MRL. Additionally, the centre of gravity of the supply chains lies outside the EU borders, favouring the Asia-Pacific axis. The lack of capacity and autonomy in the supply chain might hinder sustainable development in defence technologies. A thoughtful risk assessment is needed while integrating such materials into new defence products to avoid sovereignty issues within the EU MS.

Although R&T is recognisable and significant within the EU, the gap of expertise and technical skills concerning the new technologies in TTM is noticeable. The mindset within academia, R&T centres and industry need to align with this sector's potentialities and clearly understand the added values and benefits.

The new EU funding programmes for research and innovation starting in 2021, namely the European Defence Fund, the Horizon Europe or the EU Space programme, are critical to drive economic growth and create more and better jobs. This seven-year cycle will provide the right setting to explore, develop, and integrate new concepts, technology and capabilities to maintain the EU technology superiority.

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